

Prospective Study and Applicability of Pulp Score to Predict Mortality and Morbidity Following Peptic Ulcer**Md. Ajmal Alam¹, Anil Kumar², Kumar Ratnesh³**¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India³Associate professor, Department of General surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This prospective observational study assessed the predictive accuracy of the Pulp score for mortality and morbidity in 50 patients with peptic ulcer disease at J.L.N.M.C.H. Bhagalpur, Bihar, from August 2020 to August 2021. The study found that higher Pulp scores were significantly associated with increased risks of mortality and major morbidity, with sensitivity and specificity ranging from 70% to 80% and 80% to 90%, respectively. The results support the Pulp score as an effective tool for risk stratification and guiding clinical management in peptic ulcer patients. Future research should focus on validating these findings in broader and more diverse populations to enhance its clinical applicability.

Keywords: Pulp score, peptic ulcer, risk stratification, predictive accuracy.

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Introduction

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) represents a significant clinical challenge due to its potential for severe complications, including hemorrhage, perforation, and gastric outlet obstruction, which can result in considerable morbidity and mortality [1,2]. The ability to accurately predict these outcomes in patients with PUD is crucial for optimizing management strategies and improving patient care. Traditional prognostic indicators, while useful, do not always provide sufficient accuracy or specificity for clinical decision-making in complex cases [3,4,5].

Recent developments in predictive scoring systems have aimed to enhance the precision of prognostic assessments in medical fields [6]. The Pulp score, a novel predictive model, has been proposed as a potentially valuable tool in the realm of peptic ulcer disease. This scoring system integrates various clinical parameters to forecast the likelihood of mortality and severe morbidity following a peptic ulcer [7,8,9].

This prospective study seeks to validate the applicability and accuracy of the Pulp score in predicting adverse outcomes in patients with peptic ulcer disease. By evaluating the score's performance in a clinical setting, this research aims to determine its utility as a practical tool in guiding therapeutic approaches and improving patient

outcomes. The findings from this study could significantly impact clinical practices by providing a more robust and reliable method for risk stratification in peptic ulcer disease.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective observational study aimed to evaluate the applicability of the Pulp score in predicting mortality and morbidity among patients diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease.

Setting: The study was conducted at J.L.N.M.C.H. Bhagalpur, Bihar, a tertiary care hospital that serves a diverse population. This setting was chosen due to its high volume of peptic ulcer cases.

Participants: A total of 50 patients were enrolled in this study. Inclusion criteria included adult patients (aged 18 and above) diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease based on clinical, endoscopic, and histopathological findings. Patients were excluded if they had co-existing malignancies, had undergone previous gastric surgery, or were unable to provide informed consent.

Data Collection: Participants were assessed using the Pulp score at admission. This score was calculated based on a set of predefined clinical and laboratory parameters identified as significant predictors of outcomes in peptic ulcer disease.

Additionally, the following data were collected for each patient: demographic information, medical history, details of ulcer disease (e.g., location, size), treatment received, and outcomes during the hospital stay.

Follow-up: Patients were followed for the duration of their hospital stay up to a maximum of one year to monitor for the primary outcomes of interest, which were mortality and major morbidity (e.g., re-bleeding, surgical intervention).

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the patient characteristics and clinical outcomes. The predictive accuracy of the Pulp score was assessed by calculating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were also generated to evaluate the overall performance of the score in predicting adverse outcomes.

Results

The study enrolled 50 patients with peptic ulcer disease, comprising 32 males and 18 females. The average age of participants was 53 years. The majority of ulcers were located in the stomach (60%) and the remainder in the duodenum. The Pulp scores at admission ranged from 2 to 9, with a median score of 5. Higher scores were associated

with increased age, presence of comorbid conditions, and more severe ulcer presentations.

During the follow-up period, 8 patients (16%) succumbed to complications related to peptic ulcer disease, which included severe bleeding and septic shock. An additional 15 patients (30%) experienced major morbidity events, such as re-bleeding or the need for surgical intervention. The remaining 27 patients (54%) had uneventful recoveries with medical management alone. The sensitivity and specificity of the Pulp score for predicting mortality were 75% and 85%, respectively. For major morbidity, the sensitivity was 73% and the specificity was 82%. The area under the ROC curve for mortality was 0.81 and for morbidity was 0.79, indicating good predictive performance.

The statistical analysis confirmed that a higher Pulp score was significantly associated with an increased risk of death and major morbidity ($p < 0.05$). Logistic regression analysis showed that for each point increase in the Pulp score, the odds of mortality increased by 2.3 times, and the odds of major morbidity increased by 1.8 times. The results of this study indicated that the Pulp score is a valuable predictive tool for assessing the risk of mortality and morbidity in patients with peptic ulcer disease. Its implementation in clinical settings could aid healthcare providers in identifying high-risk patients who might benefit from more aggressive and targeted interventions.

Table 1: This table highlights how the Pulp score correlates with clinical outcomes, showing a trend where higher scores are associated with increased rates of mortality and morbidity.

Pulp Score Range	Number of Patients	Deaths	Major Morbidity Events	Patients with Uncomplicated Recovery	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
2-4	20	1	2	17	70	80
5-7	18	3	6	9	75	85
8-9	12	4	7	1	80	90

Discussion

The findings of this study underscore the predictive validity of the Pulp score in assessing mortality and morbidity risks in patients with peptic ulcer disease. The results revealed a clear correlation between higher Pulp scores and increased adverse outcomes, which supports the utility of this scoring system in clinical settings [10,11]. Specifically, patients with scores in the higher range (8-9) exhibited significantly higher rates of mortality and morbidity compared to those in the lower score ranges (2-4 and 5-7). This gradient suggests that the Pulp score can effectively stratify patients according to risk levels, thus potentially guiding more tailored treatment interventions [12].

The sensitivity and specificity values obtained (ranging from 70% to 80% and 80% to 90%, respectively, across the score ranges) demonstrate that the Pulp score is a reliable tool for predicting severe outcomes in peptic ulcer patients [13]. These metrics are particularly compelling, indicating that the score can serve as a practical guide in clinical decision-making processes by identifying high-risk patients who may require immediate and aggressive management [14].

Moreover, the statistical significance of the association between higher Pulp scores and increased risk of death and major morbidity highlights its potential as a prognostic tool in gastroenterology [15]. The ability of the Pulp score

to predict outcomes could be integrated into clinical workflows, aiding in the optimization of resource allocation and potentially improving overall patient outcomes through proactive management [16].

However, the study is not without limitations. The relatively small sample size and the single-center design may affect the generalizability of the findings [17]. Future studies involving a larger cohort and multiple centers could provide more definitive evidence of the score's applicability across different clinical settings and populations. Additionally, further research might explore the integration of the Pulp score with other diagnostic tools and health technologies to enhance predictive accuracy and clinical utility [18,19,20].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that the Pulp score is a valuable predictive tool for assessing the risk of mortality and morbidity in patients with peptic ulcer disease. Our findings indicated a strong correlation between higher Pulp scores and increased adverse outcomes, highlighting the score's effectiveness in risk stratification. With its high sensitivity and specificity, the Pulp score can aid clinicians in identifying patients at higher risk of complications, thereby facilitating more targeted and timely interventions. While promising, these results also suggest the need for further validation through larger, multi-center studies to confirm the score's generalizability and potential integration into routine clinical practice.

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